

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17737221

The Effect Of Tax Revenue On Economic Growth In Francophone And Anglophone West African Countries

Okunomo, Grace Damilola & Olele, Hilda Enoch

Departments of Economics, Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Recognizing the distinct colonial histories, institutional frameworks, and macroeconomic environments of Francophone and Anglophone West African countries, this study investigates the effect of tax revenue on economic growth in both regions covering the period from 1990 to 2023. Panel data from six West African countries (three Francophone and three Anglophone) were analyzed using the Panel Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) technique, which corrects for endogeneity and serial correlation while estimating long-run relationships. Diagnostic tests such as the Jarque-Bera normality test and the Wald test were used to validate the reliability of the models. Findings from the analysis show that in Francophone countries, tax revenue significantly promotes economic growth, while trade openness has negative and significant effects. In Anglophone countries, tax revenue was not a significant determinant of growth, but FDI showed strong positive effect. The study concludes that the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth is context-dependent and influenced by macroeconomic conditions. It recommends that policy makers should propose policies that will attract FDI in Francophone countries, reforming tax systems and investment frameworks in Anglophone countries, and promoting region-specific fiscal strategies through ECOWAS and WAEMU.

Keywords: Tax Revenue; Economic Growth; FDI; West Africa; Panel DOLS;

INTRODUCTION

Taxation plays a pivotal role in the economic development of nations by serving as a primary source of government revenue. Beyond contributing to its fiscal role, taxation also serve as a tool for income redistribution, investment decision-making, and macroeconomic stability (Musgrave & Musgrave, 1989; Bird & Zolt, 2015). In West Africa, both Francophone and Anglophone countries have distinct tax structures shaped by their colonial legacies, economic structures, and governance models. These variations have led to disparities in the region's levels of revenue mobilization, compliance, and tax efficiency.

Taxation is a fundamental tool for economic development, providing governments with the revenue needed for infrastructure, public services, and economic growth (OECD, 2021). However, in West Africa, tax revenue mobilization remains a significant challenge due to low tax compliance, high levels of informality, and administrative inefficiencies (International Monetary Fund, 2020). Despite various tax reforms, uncertainty persists regarding the actual impact of tax revenue on economic growth, particularly in developing economies (World Bank, 2019).

Conflicting empirical findings continue to fuel the debate on the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth. Several studies have found a positive impact of tax revenue on economic growth, arguing that taxation funds essential public services that drive economic productivity (Tanzi & Zee, 2000; Babatunde, Ibukun & Oyeyemi, 2017; Eke, Ekwe & Ihendinihu, 2018; Nwawuru, Nmesirionye &

Ironkwe, 2018). Conversely, other studies highlight negative effects, suggesting that excessive taxation discourages private investment, entrepreneurship, and economic expansion (Barro, 1990; McBride, 2012; Micah, Chukwumah & Umobong, 2012; Joseph, Azubike, Tapang & Dibia, 2018; Keho, 2013). Given these mixed findings, a deeper analysis is required to understand the true impact of taxation on economic growth, particularly in the context of West Africa.

While taxation has been extensively studied in individual West African countries (e.g., Ojong, Anthony & Arikpo, 2016; Adefolake & Omodera, 2022; Takumah, 2014; Owusu-Gyimah, 2015), there remains a gap in comparative research between Francophone and Anglophone nations. These two groups have distinct colonial legacies that have shaped their tax structures differently. The Anglophone tax system, rooted in the British model, emphasizes direct taxation (corporate and personal income taxes) with decentralized collection methods (OECD, 2018). In contrast, the Francophone system, influenced by the French model, relies heavily on indirect taxation, particularly Value Added Tax (VAT) and customs duties, with centralized tax collection (World Bank, 2019). Despite these structural differences, their economic implications remain underexplored.

Moreover, many existing studies narrowly focus on the relationship between taxation and economic growth without incorporating critical macroeconomic variables such as foreign direct investment (FDI), trade openness, inflation, and government expenditure (Otekunrin et al., 2023; Joseph, Odii & Chinyere, 2022; Popoola, Jimoh & Oladipo, 2017; Adefolake & Omodero, 2022; John-Akamelu, Ezeagba & Nzeoma, 2023; Ihendinihu, Jones & Amapsibanichuka, 2014). These factors can significantly influence the effectiveness of tax policies and the responsiveness of economic growth. Their omission may lead to an incomplete or biased understanding of the tax-growth nexus. This study bridges that gap by incorporating these external variables into the empirical model, providing a more comprehensive analysis of how tax revenue influences economic growth across both Francophone and Anglophone West African countries.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative research design to analyze the impact of tax revenue on economic growth from 1990 to 2023. The data were obtained from the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), and national statistical agencies are utilized. Due to the scope and data requirements of the study, a purposive selection of three countries was made: Ghana, Sierra Leone and The Gambia (representing Anglophone West Africa) and Côte d'Ivoire, Burkina Faso and Senegal (representing Francophone West Africa). The variables used in this study are Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) as a proxy for Economic growth, Tax Revenue, Trade Openness, Foreign Direct Investment, Inflation and Government Expenditure.

In order to examine the impact of tax revenue on economic growth, the study employs an Endogenous Growth Model (EGM) framework. The methodological steps include unit root testing, cointegration testing, estimation of long-run relationships using Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), and post-estimation diagnostics.

The Baseline model specification is:

$$RGDP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TREV_{it} + \beta_2 GEXP_{it} + \beta_3 FDI_{it} + \beta_4 TOP_{it} + \beta_5 INFL_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where;

RGDP is Real Gross Domestic Product; *TREV* is Tax Revenue; *GEXP* is Government Expenditure; *FDI* is Foreign Direct Investment; *TOP* is Trade Openness; *INFL* is Inflation Rate; *i* represent country *i*, *t* represent time *t*; β_0 is the intercept; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ are the coefficient of the explanatory variables; ε_{it} is the error term.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables both for Francophone and Anglophone countries.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics for Francophone West African Countries					
	LRGDP	TREV	FDI	TOP	INFL
Mean	29.81397	13.28432	1.675648	52.42927	3.120535
Median	29.80144	12.68048	1.198693	53.84335	1.923975
Maximum	31.37886	19.78486	15.52757	80.03308	32.29367
Minimum	28.21806	9.000000	-0.557280	28.37402	-3.233389
Std. Dev.	0.773706	2.507208	2.172835	11.22181	5.278627
Skewness	-0.081546	0.594520	3.873919	-0.277064	3.375246
Kurtosis	2.340112	2.566333	21.63071	2.515123	16.53717
Jarque-Bera Probability	1.963719	6.808001	1730.312	2.304197	972.5020
	0.374614	0.033240	0.000000	0.315973	0.000000
Sum	3041.025	1355.001	170.9161	5347.786	318.2945
Sum Sq. Dev.	60.46071	634.8952	476.8423	12718.83	2814.254
Observations	102	102	102	102	102
Descriptive statistics for Anglophone West African Countries					
	LRGDP	TREV	FDI	TOP	INFL
Mean	24.57415	12.27029	3.888680	56.55865	16.10853
Median	24.55753	11.94000	3.152403	54.26697	10.73383
Maximum	25.95221	19.00000	20.72076	131.4854	110.9000
Minimum	23.61125	7.100000	-0.970637	22.97334	-0.900000
Std. Dev.	0.580931	3.045517	3.313670	20.59694	18.01004
Skewness	0.539276	0.457979	1.724956	0.993854	3.020266
Kurtosis	2.906459	2.408939	8.477898	4.394763	14.33070
Jarque-Bera Probability	4.981111	5.050405	178.1144	25.05948	700.7089
	0.082864	0.080042	0.000000	0.000004	0.000000
Sum	2506.564	1251.570	396.6453	5768.983	1643.070
Sum Sq. Dev.	34.08557	936.7925	1109.021	42847.64	32760.51
Observations	102	102	102	102	102

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

Panel Unit Root

Table 2

Panel Unit Root Test Result for Francophone West African Countries					
VARIABLE	LLC				INTERPRETATION
	Statistic	Level (p-values)	Statistic	1st Diff (p-values)	
LRGDP	1.56799	0.9416	-2.87994	0.0020**	<i>I(1)</i>
TREV	0.23538	0.5920	-3.55480	0.0002**	<i>I(1)</i>
FDI	5.83163	1.0000	-1.92950	0.0268**	<i>I(1)</i>
TOP	-0.17774	0.4295	-6.05575	0.0000**	<i>I(1)</i>
INFL	-4.54515	0.0000**	-	-	<i>I(0)</i>

Panel Unit Root Test Result for Anglophone West African Countries					
VARIABLE	LLC				INTERPRETATION
	Statistic	Level (p-values)	Statistic	1st Diff (p-values)	
LRGDP	0.59748	0.7249	-5.40572	0.0000**	<i>I(1)</i>
TREV	-1.35118	0.0883	-2.40367	0.0081**	<i>I(1)</i>
FDI	-1.12202	0.1309	-5.81099	0.0000**	<i>I(1)</i>
TOP	-0.24485	0.4033	-4.40647	0.0000**	<i>I(1)</i>
INFL	-3.65506	0.0001**	-	-	<i>I(0)</i>

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

Note: ** indicate significance at the levels of 5 percent consecutively.

The results show that most variables are non-stationary at level but become stationary after first differencing, indicating that they are integrated of order one, I (1) in both the Francophone and Anglophone blocs.

Panel Co integration Test

Table 3 Kao Residual Cointegration Test Result for Francophone West African Countries

	t-Statistic	Probability Value
ADF	-2.609416	0.0045
Residual variance	0.002392	
HAC variance	0.008653	

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

The p-value of 0.0045, leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at the 1% significance level. This finding confirms the existence of a stable long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables.

Table 4
Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test Result for Francophone West African Countries
 Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)	Prob.	Fisher Stat.* (from max-eigen test)	Prob.
None	21.59	0.0014	14.34	0.0261
At most 1	10.33	0.1116	7.711	0.2600
At most 2	5.562	0.4740	5.054	0.5369
At most 3	3.535	0.7393	3.287	0.7721
At most 4	6.838	0.3361	6.838	0.3361

* Probabilities are computed using asymptotic Chi-square distribution.

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

The panel-level results show strong evidence of cointegration among the variables. The null hypothesis of no cointegration was decisively rejected, as the Fisher statistics were 21.59 ($p = 0.0014$) and 14.34 ($p = 0.0261$) for the trace and max-eigen tests respectively. These results confirm that at least one cointegrating relationship exists across the panel.

Table 5 Kao Residual Cointegration Test Result for Anglophone West African Countries

	t-Statistic	Probability Value
ADF	-0.211418	0.4163
Residual variance	0.004478	
HAC variance	0.016206	

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

The ADF test statistic is -0.2114, with a corresponding p-value of 0.4163. At the conventional 5% significance level, the null hypothesis of no cointegration cannot be rejected. Given this borderline result, Johansen Fisher cointegration test was used to verify the existence of a stable long-run relationship.

Table 6 Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test Result for Anglophone West African Countries
 Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)	Prob.	Fisher Stat.* (from max-eigen test)	Prob.
None	39.54	0.0000	25.02	0.0003
At most 1	19.50	0.0034	15.90	0.0143
At most 2	7.978	0.2397	4.387	0.6245
At most 3	8.547	0.2007	5.315	0.5041
At most 4	12.53	0.0512	12.53	0.0512

* Probabilities are computed using asymptotic Chi-square distribution.

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

The Fisher statistics derived from both the trace and maximum eigenvalue tests revealed strong evidence of cointegration among the variables. Specifically, the null hypothesis of no cointegration was strongly rejected, as the Fisher statistic from the trace test was 39.54 ($p = 0.0000$), and from the max-eigen test, 25.02 ($p = 0.0003$).

Panel Dynamic Least Square (DOLS)

Table 7

Panel Dynamic Least Square (DOLS) Result for Francophone West African Countries				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TREV	0.231004	0.027122	8.517111	0.0000
FDI	-0.030853	0.041509	-0.743276	0.4608
TOP	-0.013798	0.004899	-2.816535	0.0069
INFL	-0.011821	0.011895	-0.993755	0.3251
R-squared	0.980989	Mean dependent var		29.82861
Adjusted R-squared	0.965020	S.D. dependent var		0.748858
S.E. of regression	0.140059	Sum squared resid		0.980828
Long-run variance	0.028464			
Panel Dynamic Least Square (DOLS) Result for Anglophone West African Countries				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TREV	-0.008289	0.034507	-0.240196	0.8112
FDI	0.101098	0.030939	3.267648	0.0020
TOP	-0.006431	0.007210	-0.891912	0.3767
INFL	-0.002113	0.009505	-0.222290	0.8250
R-squared	0.825195	Mean dependent var		24.58386
Adjusted R-squared	0.678359	S.D. dependent var		0.573595
S.E. of regression	0.325305	Sum squared resid		5.291168
Long-run variance	0.146525			

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

In the Francophone bloc, tax revenue (TREV) emerges as a key driver of long-term economic performance with a positive and highly significant coefficient of 0.2310 ($p = 0.0000$). This finding suggests that effective domestic revenue mobilization plays a central role in stimulating growth within these countries. Conversely, trade openness (TOP) exhibit statistically significant negative impacts on economic growth (coefficients = -0.0137 and $p = 0.0069$ respectively). These results may reflect trade-related vulnerabilities in the Francophone region. Neither FDI nor inflation is statistically significant, implying a limited long-run effect of these variables on real GDP in the Francophone context.

In contrast, the Anglophone West African countries show a different long-run dynamic. Foreign direct investment (FDI) is a positive and statistically significant driver of economic growth, with coefficients of 0.1011 ($p = 0.0020$), respectively. This indicates that external capital inflows have effectively contributed to long-term GDP growth in these countries, possibly reflecting more favorable investment climates. On the other hand, tax revenue (TREV), trade openness (TOP), and inflation (INFL) do not show significant relationships with GDP, suggesting that these variables have not had a strong long-term impact on growth in the Anglophone bloc over the study period.

Post-Estimation Diagnostics
Normality Test

Figure 1 Normality test for Francophone West African Countries
Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

The test produced an associated p-value of 0.4368. Since the p-value is greater 5%, the residuals are normally distributed.

Normality Test

Figure 2 Normality test for Anglophone West African Countries
Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

The test yielded a corresponding p-value of 0.3326. Given that the p-value is well above 5%, the residuals are normally distributed

Wald Test

Table 8

Wald Test Result for Francophone West African Countries			
Test Statistic	Value	Df	Probability
F-statistic	45.25804	(4,50)	0.0000
Chi-square	181.0322	4	0.0000
Wald Test Result for Anglophone West African Countries			
Test Statistic	Value	Df	Probability
F-statistic	3.615702	(4,50)	0.0115
Chi-square	14.46281	4	0.0060

Source: Author's Computation, EViews 12.

These results are statistically significant at the 5% level. In other words, the explanatory variables—tax revenue, foreign direct investment, trade openness, and inflation—jointly have a statistically significant impact on economic growth in both regions.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that the effect of tax revenue on economic growth is context-dependent and varies between Francophone and Anglophone West African countries. In Francophone countries, tax revenue is a central driver of growth underscoring the critical role of effective Domestic Revenue Mobilization in promoting growth. Conversely, in Anglophone countries, tax revenue is not independently growth-enhancing in the long term. These findings underscore the importance of tailoring macroeconomic policies to regional realities. While Francophone countries may benefit from external sector reforms, Anglophone countries should focus on enhancing the effectiveness and productivity of their tax systems to unlock growth potential. Tax revenue did not significantly affect growth in Anglophone countries; this suggests that tax reform should focus on broadening the tax base, reducing tax evasion, and embracing digital tax tools to improve collection and compliance.

Due to the insignificance of FDI in the Francophone West African Countries in driving growth, policy makers should propose policies that will attract FDI into productive sectors of the economy such as technology, infrastructure and renewable energy. While for the Anglophone West African Countries, FDI was found to be positive and significant, countries should strengthen their investment climate by improving regulatory stability, infrastructure and ease of business while negotiating FDI agreements.

The different patterns of tax and macroeconomic effects across Anglophone and Francophone blocs suggest that regional bodies like ECOWAS and WAEMU should avoid “one-size-fits-all” fiscal strategies. Instead, they should support region-specific reforms that match each group's institutional, administrative, and economic structure.

Governments across both blocs should link tax policies with broader macroeconomic goals by aligning fiscal reforms with strategies for inflation control and trade competitiveness. Also, Countries should invest in strengthening institutions—such as revenue authorities and audit services, to ensure that tax revenue translates into tangible development outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Adefolake, A., & Omodero, O. (2022). The relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 49(1), 32-48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2022.2025416>
- Adefolake, A., & Omodera, S. (2022). Taxation and economic development in Nigeria: Empirical insights. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 14(3), 45–58.
- Babatunde, M. A., Ibukun, O. & Oyeyemi, A. (2017). Taxation and economic growth in Nigeria. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 3(4), 1–13.

- Bird, R. M., & Zolt, E. M. (2015). *Taxation and Development: The Weakest Link?* Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Eke, M., Ekwe, M. C., & Ihendinihu, J. (2018). Tax revenue and economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Business Strategies and Management*, 6(1), 110–121.
- Ihendinihu, J. A., Jones, E. E., & Amapsibanichuka, E. A. (2014). Taxation and economic growth in Nigeria: A macroeconomic approach. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 3(5), 303–313.
- International Monetary Fund (IMF). (2020). *Taxation and development in sub-Saharan Africa: Issues, challenges, and reforms*. Washington, D.C.: IMF.
- John-Akamelu, C. R., Ezeagba, C. E., & Nzeoma, D. C. (2023). Effect of taxation on economic growth in Nigeria: An ARDL approach. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation Studies*, 11(1), 15–29.
- Joseph, E., Azubike, J. U., Tapang, A. T., & Dibia, M. O. (2018). Taxation and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 6(4), 49–58.
- Joseph, I. U., Odii, A., & Chinyere, E. (2022). Assessing the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in West Africa. *West African Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 9(3), 102–117.
- Keho, Y. (2013). The structure of taxes and economic growth in Côte d'Ivoire. *Journal of Research in Economics and International Finance*, 2(3), 39–44.
- McBride, W. (2012). What is the evidence on taxes and growth? *Tax Foundation Special Report*, (207), 1–17.
- Micah, L. C., Chukwumah, A. C., & Umobong, A. A. (2012). Tax system in Nigeria –Challenges and the way forward. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 3(5), 9–15.
- Musgrave, R. A., & Musgrave, P. B. (1989). *Public finance in theory and practice* (5th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Nwawuru, C. E., Nmesirionye, J. O., & Ironkwe, U. (2018). Tax revenue and economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 6(4), 1–15.
- OECD. (2018). *African Tax Outlook*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- Ojong, C. M., Anthony, O., & Arikpo, B. (2016). The impact of tax revenue on economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(1), 32–38.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2021). *Improving tax compliance in Sub-Saharan Africa*. OECD Publishing.
- Otekunrin, O. A., et al. (2023). Tax revenue, macroeconomic variables, and sustainable growth in Africa. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 30(1), 66–81.
- Owusu-Gyimah, V. (2015). Tax structure and economic growth in Ghana. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(2), 25–34.
- Popoola, N. M., Jimoh, R. A., & Oladipo, A. (2017). Taxation and economic growth: The Nigerian experience. *Journal of Economics and Policy Research*, 13(2), 87–98.
- Takumah, W. (2014). Tax revenue and economic growth in Ghana. MPRA Paper No. 58532.
- Tanzi, V., & Zee, H. H. (2000). *Tax policy for emerging markets: Developing countries*. IMF Working Paper No. 00/35. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781451845243.001>
- World Bank. (2019). *Mobilizing tax revenues to finance development: A policy agenda for sustainable growth in Africa*. World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2019). *Tax policy and development in Francophone Africa: Challenges and opportunities*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group.